

Center for Ethical and Socially
Responsible Leadership
MICHIGAN STATE UNIVERSITY

Our Common Commitment on Social and Business Responsibility: Statement of the Conference, held at XLRI, Jamshedpur, February 2-3, 2024 Executive Summary

The Conference on Social and Business Responsibility, titled "Enabling Social and Business Responsibility in Our Globalised World," held at XLRI, Xavier School of Management, Jamshedpur, India on February 2-3, 2024, brought together approximately 180 thought leaders, practitioners, and academics from around the world. Organised by XLRI, Xavier School of Management's JRD Tata Foundation and four foreign universities, the conference aimed to affirm a shared commitment towards fostering ethical, sustainable, and socially responsible business practices amidst global challenges such as climate change, social inequality, and corporate governance failures.

The conference provided an intellectually stimulating platform for rethinking concepts of ethics and responsibility in the contemporary world. Shifting perspectives call for a concerted effort to understand the changes wrought by globalization and the digital revolution. It emphasized the role of academia in keeping pace with emerging trends, questioning their effectiveness, ethics, and accountability, and fostering interdisciplinary dialogue to address societal challenges.

Key themes emerged from the discussions, including:

- **Recognition of Business Impact:** Businesses must recognize their influence on societal and environmental landscapes, striving to ensure a positive impact through economic, social, and environmental sustainability.
- **Transparency and Accountability:** Open and accountable practices enhance stakeholder trust, necessitating clear reporting of actions, outcomes, and policies related to corporate governance, environmental stewardship, and social responsibility.
- **Urgency of Climate Action:** Businesses must acknowledge their role in combating climate change by adopting sustainable practices that minimize environmental harm and promote planetary health.
- **Embracing Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion:** Diversity, equity, and inclusion within workplaces foster innovation, employee satisfaction, and societal progress.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Effective stakeholder engagement involves listening and responding to the needs and concerns of those impacted by business activities, ensuring decisions are informed and considerate of diverse perspectives.
- **Innovation for the Common Good:** Innovation should be harnessed not only for economic gain but also for solving societal challenges, promoting sustainability, and enhancing quality of life for all.
- **Ethical Leadership:** Leaders must exemplify ethical behaviour, inspiring integrity, respect, and responsibility throughout organizations and industries.
- **Continuous Learning and Evaluation:** Continuous education in ethics and responsibility equips businesses to navigate ethical dilemmas and complex global challenges, while continuous evaluation and improvement of ethical practices ensures long-term sustainability.

The conference concluded with a call to action for participants to embody these principles in their personal and professional endeavours, fostering a global community dedicated to the common good and sustainable development.

Date: February 3, 2024

XLRI, Xavier School of Management, Jamshedpur

www.xlri.ac.in

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Our Common Commitment on Social and Business Responsibility: Statement of the Conference, held at XLRI, Jamshedpur, February 2-3, 2024

In an era where global challenges such as climate change, social inequality, and corporate governance failures increasingly demand our attention, the responsibility of business in society is more critical than ever before. This conference, organised by XLRI, Xavier School of Management, JRD Tata Foundation, Jamshedpur, in collaboration with four foreign universities, "Enabling Social and Business Responsibility in Our Globalised World" brought together about 180 thought leaders, practitioners, and academics from around the globe to affirm a shared commitment towards fostering ethical, sustainable, and socially responsible business practices. As we encounter the dynamic, complex and interconnected world, it is imperative that businesses not only drive economic growth but also contribute positively to societal and environmental well-being. As participants of this conference, we accept the following statements and commit ourselves to fulfil them in our personal and professional lives, which are derived from our discussions and sharing, as we seek to redefine the ethos of business in the 21st century.

The intellectually stimulating conference offered a well-designed framework for rethinking previously known concepts of ethics and responsibility. Shifting perspectives in the contemporary world call for a joint effort to try to understand the changes the globalized world is going through today. From its beginnings, the digital revolution has reshaped academic and business thought and we need to make a sustainable intellectual platform to engage with new concepts and ideas critically. We have entered new, uncharted, territory that we do not know much about and our interdisciplinary efforts must help chart a course through it. The role of academia and research institutions is to keep pace with the upcoming trends and question their effectiveness, ethics, accountability, and possible outcomes. At the interface of technology and human values, we need to raise ethical awareness and foster a better understanding of responsibility in business. This will be done by bringing together people on the international level to systematically discuss the ethical, social, and intellectual challenges. Not in the way of taking sides, optimistic or pessimistic, but rather seeing things from different angles.

- **Acknowledging Business Impact:** Businesses must recognize their vast influence on societal and environmental landscapes and strive to ensure that this impact is positive, fostering economic, social, and environmental sustainability through their operations and strategies. This will be particularly true of Artificial Intelligence and other emerging technologies, which will be impacting us greatly in the coming years. We need to deal with these technologies ethically and responsibly.
- **Transparency and Accountability:** Committing to open and accountable practices enhances stakeholder trust. This involves clear reporting of actions, outcomes, and policies related to corporate governance, environmental stewardship, and social responsibility.
- **Community Contribution:** Businesses should actively contribute to the prosperity of the communities in which they operate, recognizing that their success is intrinsically linked to the well-being of these communities.
- **Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion:** Embracing diversity and ensuring equity and inclusion within workplaces are crucial for fostering innovation, employee satisfaction, and societal progress.

- **Urgency of Climate Action:** Businesses must acknowledge their role in combating climate change, adopting sustainable practices that minimize environmental harm and promote the health of our planet.
- **Compassionate Capitalism:** Reimagining capitalism with a focus on compassion and social responsibility ensures that businesses contribute to societal well-being, balancing profit with purpose.
- **Moral Imperative of Ethics:** Ethical business practices transcend legal obligations, rooted in a moral imperative that guides companies in making decisions that are right and just. Here CSR and ESG practices become very relevant. This demands spiritual basis and sound psychological balance, especially from the business leaders.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Effective stakeholder engagement involves listening and responding to the needs and concerns of those impacted by business activities, ensuring decisions are informed and considerate of diverse perspectives.
- **Innovation for the Common Good:** Innovation should be harnessed not only for economic gain but also for solving societal challenges, promoting sustainability, and enhancing the quality of life for all. Thus, we can become forces for the Good, personally, professionally and collectively.
- **Global Cooperation:** Addressing global business ethics, sustainability, and social responsibility challenges requires international collaboration and partnerships, leveraging collective strengths for common goals.
- **Education and Continuous Learning:** Committing to the continuous education of leaders and employees in ethics and responsibility ensures that businesses are equipped to navigate ethical dilemmas and complex global challenges.
- **Redefining Financial Success:** Financial success should encompass positive social and environmental impact, recognizing that true prosperity includes the well-being of all stakeholders.
- **Ethical Leadership:** Leaders must exemplify ethical behaviour, inspiring integrity, respect, and responsibility throughout their organizations and industries. They must create ethical corporate cultures where all employees can act with integrity. While working for the greater good, they should specifically look into the needs of the marginalized and socially ostracized.
- **Evaluating Ethical Practices:** Continuous evaluation and improvement of ethical practices are essential for adapting to evolving societal expectations and ensuring long-term sustainability. This can lead to a culture of excellence and integrity, both at the personal and professional levels.
- **Interconnectedness and Equitability:** Recognizing the interconnectedness of global stakeholders compels businesses to foster an equitable, sustainable, and beneficial ecosystem for all involved.

Thus, it becomes evident that the path towards enabling social and business responsibility in our globalized world requires concerted effort, unwavering commitment, and innovative thinking from all sectors of society. The conference serves as a pivotal platform for exchanging ideas, forging partnerships, and catalysing action towards this noble goal. By affirming these statements, participants commit to not only discussing these principles but also embodying them in their professional endeavours. Let us move forward with a shared vision of a world where businesses act as stewards of ethical values, environmental sustainability, and social prosperity, paving the way for a future that honours the dignity of all beings and the planet we call home. Thus, we shall create a global community of excellence and integrity, committed to the common good of all stakeholders involved! This will foster the greater good and make us all sources of and forces for the Good!

Jamshedpur
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